

Abstract

Attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) is a common neurodevelopmental disorder with a prevalence of 5.9% during childhood/adolescence and 2.5% during adulthood. ADHD is associated with lower IQ scored and more poorly rated academic abilities. ADHD carries the stigma of being the consequence of modern lifestyle, which negatively affects the well-being of people with ADHD. Teenagers and adolescents in particular are more sensitive to peer influence and are thus more sensitive to negative believes regarding ADHD from their peers.

We created a workshop about ADHD to reduce the stigma around it and investigated the effect of this workshop on the VMBO students' understanding of and attitude towards people with ADHD. This effect was measured by collecting data from three groups: a focus group, VMBO students and their teachers. The focus group provided feedback on different components of the workshop. The VMBO students received a measurement question form before and after the workshop and the teachers received an evaluation form during the workshop to evaluate the workshop and the aims of the study. In addition to this, observations were made during the workshop on the reaction of the VMBO students to provide a more nuanced insight to better understand the results.

The workshop about ADHD resulted in a significant increase in the VMBO students' understanding of ADHD, but was not enough to significantly increase their positive attitude towards ADHD. However, according to the teachers, the VMBO students understanding of and attitude towards people with ADHD had both increased.

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Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Full version
ADHD	Attention-deficit/hyperactive disorder
VMBO	Vorbereidend middelbaar beroepsonderwijs (lowest school level of high school in the Netherlands).

Chapter 1: Introduction

This research report describes a study on the impact of a workshop about ADHD, given to high school VMBO students. The aim of this workshop is to reduce the stigma that ADHD carries by increasing the VMBO students' knowledge and by promoting a positive attitude towards people with ADHD.

1.1 What is ADHD?

1.1.1 ADHD according to the DSM-5

Attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) is a common neurodevelopmental condition that typically emerges during childhood with a prevalence of 5.9% and 2.5% during childhood/adolescence and adulthood, respectively (1). Until the late 20th century, it was believed that ADHD only occurred in children and adolescents but not in adults. However, it is now believed that ADHD can continue from childhood into adulthood and that ADHD can thus also be diagnosed in adults (2).

In the fifth edition of the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (DSM-5), ADHD is defined as a "persistent pattern of inattention and/or hyperactivity-impulsivity that interferes with functioning or development" (3). There are three overall subtypes of ADHD: the predominantly inattentive type; the predominantly hyperactive/impulsive type; and the combined type (4). The main characteristics are thus impulsivity, hyperactivity and inattention. School-age boys mainly exhibit the externalizing characteristics, such as hyperactivity and impulsivity, whereas girls mainly show more inattentive symptoms and less openly disturbing behaviours (2). Therefore, ADHD still often remains undiagnosed in girls (2).

Revision of the diagnostic criteria in the DSM for ADHD in 2013 led to an increasing prevalence of ADHD in children, adolescents and adults (5). The three most important revisions were the increase of age of onset from 7 to 12 years; the decrease of the symptom threshold from six to five symptoms for patients from the age of 17 years and older; and lastly, the reconceptualization of ADHD as a neurodevelopmental disorder instead of a disruptive behavioural disorder. The revisions also allowed for the diagnosis of ADHD to be present alongside other conditions, such as autism spectrum disorder (5). These alterations reduce the chance of the diagnosis of ADHD being overlooked by clinicians, especially in adulthood and adulthood (6).

1.1.2 Characteristics of ADHD

There is much heterogeneity in expression of characteristics and behaviour in both boys and girls (7). The main characteristics hyperactivity, impulsivity and inattention could express themselves in multiple ways. Examples of these expressions are internal restlessness, ceaseless unfocused mental activity, difficulties focussing on conversations and problems with self-regulation. Difficulties people with ADHD also deal with are controlling impulses, regulating emotional responses, solving problems, switching attention and initiating tasks. Other common issues experienced by patients with ADHD is low self-esteem and sleep problems (2, 8). Moreover, ADHD is associated with lower IQ scores (2).

Different cognitive domains can be affected in people with ADHD. Executive functioning is one of these cognitive domains. Deficits in this domain are seen in verbal and visuospatial working memory, vigilance, planning and inhibitory control. Reward dysregulation is also a characterization of ADHD. It can express itself in multiple ways in patients with ADHD, like preferring immediate rewards over delayed ones, overestimating the magnitude of those immediate rewards and making suboptimal decisions (5). Deficits that could be apparent in other domains are temporal information processing and timing; memory span; motor control, speech and language; processing speed and response time variability; and arousal and activation. The amount of deficits differs per patient, but most patients show deficits in one or two cognitive domains (5).

There are also positive aspects associated with ADHD. According to a qualitative study done by Schippers et al., positive characteristics of ADHD are creativity, flexibility, higher-order cognitive skills, socio-affective skills and being dynamic. Being honest and open-minded were also named positive aspects of ADHD. However, research on the positive aspects of ADHD is still limited (9).

1.1.3 Aetiology of ADHD

In the aetiology of ADHD, both genetic and environmental risk factors play a role (5). A genetic risk factor is its heritability of 70-80%; ADHD often runs in families. Genome-wide association studies show that most ADHD associated-genes regulate the ADHD symptoms expressed in people with ADHD. For example, genes associated with hyperactivity and impulsivity regulate noradrenaline, serotonin, dopamine and neurite outgrowth systems. Other analyses showed abnormalities in the function and structure of the brain in people with ADHD, such as alterations in the white matter integrity. This was especially visible in the right forceps minor, bilateral internal capsule, right anterior corona radiata and the left cerebellum. They also found smaller volumes across several brain regions, like the right putamen, globus pallidus, cerebellum and the caudate nucleus (5).

There are a lot of environmental factors that influence the expression of ADHD in people. These factors can be peer-, family-, school- neighbourhood-, and/or policy-related (10). A child with ADHD can experience more challenges when they grow up in a small house together with a lot of children compared to when they grow up in a big house with a lot of space. It is important to keep these environmental factors in mind when trying to understand and help someone with ADHD. Other environmental risk factors that are associated with ADHD are maternal smoking, early maternal deprivation, maternal alcohol use, premature birth, low birth weight and exposure to several toxins, such as polychlorinated biphenyls, lead, zinc and phosphate pesticides (5). Some patients develop secondary ADHD after brain injury (2).

1.1.4 ADHD in relation to other conditions

Characteristics of ADHD can partially overlap with other psychiatric and non-psychiatric conditions. Characteristics can also overlap with some physiological states and somatic diseases, such as over-exhaustion and sleep deprivation (11). The pattern of comorbidities changes over the lifespan of people with ADHD. Comorbidities most seen in children are conduct disorder and oppositional defiant disorder. 20-50% of children with ADHD also have characteristics of autistic spectrum disorders (2). This high percentage can be attributed to their shared genetic heritability and their association with the same impairments in social functioning and executive functioning (2, 12). 10-20% of children with ADHD has a tic disorder, as opposed to 3-4% in the whole population. 25-40% of the patients with ADHD has major reading and writing problems. Moreover, boys with ADHD tend to have more learning problems compared to girls (2).

Comorbidities of ADHD most seen in adults are substance use disorders, mood and anxiety disorders, depression, antisocial personality disorders, sleep disorders and somatic diseases (2). The level of comorbid disorders are similar between men and women, but the referral rates differ. This is because women are more likely to seek help than men. ADHD is often not recognised in adults due to the overlap of ADHD characteristics with psychopathological characteristics in comorbid disorders (13, 14).

1.1.5 Transition from childhood to adulthood

The presentation of the characteristics of ADHD and the pattern of comorbidities can change throughout the lifespan of patients. The presentation of the characteristics are also more similar between the sexes in adulthood than in childhood (2). This also explains why the proportion of males is 80% in child and adolescent clinics, but 50% in adult clinics (8). ADHD characteristics such as

impulsivity and hyperactivity can decline from later adolescence, but difficulties with education, time management, organization, employment and relationships usually persists (2, 14).

Young adulthood is an important developmental period in which you manage employment, education and relationships. During this period, people also become more independent from their parents. During the developmental stages of puberty and adolescence, people go through a huge cognitive development in which executive functioning capabilities are developed. These capabilities facilitate self-regulation of thoughts, emotions and actions. The increase in self-regulatory control leads to deductive reasoning, information processing, efficiency and the capacity for planned, hypothetical, abstract and multidimensional thinking, which become more important in high school (15). In people with ADHD, this development is delayed and in some cases, it does not happen (14). Completing homework, being prepared for class and managing work are challenges children with ADHD can struggle with, which makes the transition to high school challenging (16). These challenges could also impact their social interactions. In particular the first year of high school, it is reported that students with ADHD have less motivation for learning than their classmates without ADHD and show less favourable attitudes towards their peers (17). In comparison with their peers, children with ADHD obtain lower grades and are rated more poorly on their academic ability. Because of this, children with ADHD are less likely to complete high school or to undertake further education (16). This can have consequences, such as unemployment, substance use, delinquency and mental health problems (17).

On top of that, teenagers and adolescents are more sensitive to peer influence and attach more value to peer acceptance than adults or children. The amount of time spent with peers also increases during the teenager years and the family and peer values start to differ (15).

ADHD is thus a neurodevelopmental disorder with a lot of heterogeneity on multiple areas, partially due to its multifactorial aetiology (5). The pattern of comorbidities and the challenges people with ADHD face changes over the lifespan of people with ADHD. However, the transition to high school can be extra challenging for people with ADHD. These challenges can influence their social interactions. Teenagers are more sensitive to peer influence and are thus more sensitive to negative beliefs regarding ADHD from their peers.

1.2 Stigma around ADHD

The diagnostic label ADHD carries a lot of stigma and prejudices, which is an underestimated risk factor for treatment adherence and efficacy, life satisfaction, symptom severity and the mental well-being of individuals with ADHD (18, 19).

Stigma regarding mental health reflects a set of negative and unfair beliefs that come from falsely assumed associations from society or a group of people about characteristics and/or behaviours from another group of people. These unfair beliefs mostly seen and expressed in social interactions. There are three types of stigma: public stigma, self-stigma and courtesy stigma. Public stigma appears when a large population accepts negative and unfair beliefs about individuals who differ in characteristics or behaviour. Public stigma often results in self-stigma, where an individual internalizes a “new degraded identity” and has these negative beliefs from society about themselves. This has a negative impact on their quality of life, social functioning and self-esteem (18, 19). Courtesy stigma occurs when a person gets negatively judged for being associated with a stigmatized person (18). The stigmatization of people with psychiatric disorders is a big concern in the field of mental health (20). This report will mainly focus on public stigma, because by reducing public stigma, self-stigma and courtesy stigma will ultimately also decrease.

ADHD carries the stigma of being a consequence of modern lifestyle (2). It is believed that a child's behaviour stems from parental failure, watching too many TV shows, excessive videogaming, substance abuse or the individual's own failure. Public stereotypic beliefs are that only children can have ADHD, adults with ADHD simulate their symptoms and that people with ADHD act without thinking. It is also thought that ADHD is invented by drug companies (19). In social context, perceived characteristics of ADHD are unpredictability, impoliteness, unreliability, emotional immaturity, disinterest in others and/or character weakness (19). In the class environment, children with ADHD are less likely to be favoured as friends by peers and more likely to be acknowledged as highly disturbing. Prejudices associated with ADHD increase in this way. Peers who believe that ADHD stems from the individual's own failure, parental failure or substance abuse, are more likely distance themselves from the child with ADHD (18).

In studies about the children's approval of peers with ADHD in comparison with peers with other conditions such as asthma, depression and children with Down Syndrome, children judged a peer with ADHD-associated behaviours more negatively than peers with other conditions. It was also found that the peer ratings were more negative if girls showed ADHD-associated behaviour than boys (18). A study done by Law et al. concluded that the levels of disapproval are more increased by the externalizing behaviour of children with ADHD and less by the diagnostic label. A lot of children do not know what the label ADHD entails and only judge behaviour (18, 21). Public stigmatizing experiences, lowered peer acceptance and false accusations in regard to ADHD-associated behaviour in children can increase internalizing stigma in children with ADHD, which can have a negative impact on the child (15, 18). This could lead to a greater social dysfunction related to ADHD (19). It is thus important to decrease public stigma on ADHD and ADHD-associated behaviour. A good way to reduce stigma is education and increasing knowledge (22). Previous research has shown that teaching 14- and 15- years old about mental health difficulties has helped to increase their knowledge about the subject, reduce stigma and promote positive attitudes towards their peers with mental health difficulties (23). It is thus not only important to educate teenagers on ADHD, but also to promote positive attitudes towards their peers with ADHD. This will reduce stigma and lead to more understanding of peers with ADHD, which will lead to a higher quality of life and more social inclusion of teenagers with ADHD (24). The ADHDplaza project focusses on reducing stigma around ADHD in VMBO high schools through a workshop about ADHD.

1.3 Reducing stigma regarding ADHD in VMBO schools

1.3.1 The ADHDplaza project

The goal of the ADHDplaza project is to connect teenagers with ADHD, their peers, their teachers, PhD students in the ADHD research field and experts on ADHD through an online platform (website and Instagram) and through a workshop about ADHD that is given to classes at different VMBO-schools. VMBO-schools are schools with the lowest school levels in the Netherlands. Prior to starting this project, a pilot study was done with 23 high school students and 1 MBO student with ADHD to measure the need for more information facilities about ADHD. This was done using an online survey. This pilot study showed that 62% of these students thought they did not know much about ADHD. The source of information about ADHD for these VMBO students were often their parents or the internet. These students also indicate that their peers know too little and that they often get told that they overexaggerate, or that ADHD does not exist. Some students also had to explain to their teacher what ADHD entails (25). The need to reduce stigma around ADHD and provide correct information about it and where to find help if people need and/or want this, is important.

It is assumed that the percentage of students with ADHD is higher in VMBO-schools in the Netherlands, due to their more poorly rated academic abilities and their association with lower IQ scores (2, 16). It is thus especially important to reduce stigma that ADHD or ADHD-associated behaviour carries in these schools (24). This is why the ADHDplaza project focusses on reducing stigma in VMBO schools.

The ADHDplaza project has four aims: 1) increase the knowledge in teenagers about ADHD by giving a workshop about ADHD; 2) receive knowledge on what the teenagers want to know about ADHD; 3) train PhD students in science communication; and 4) more connection between science and young people with ADHD. Each PhD student gave one workshop and was an assistant during another workshop. The learning goals of the PhD students were part of the ADHDplaza project, but did not form a part of this research. During the workshop, the students were asked what they wanted to know about ADHD. PhD-students made small movies where they answered some of these questions and they were put on the website to encourage the teenagers to visit the website. With the workshop and the online platforms, we aimed to increase the VMBO students' knowledge and to promote positive attitudes towards their peers with ADHD, to reduce stigma on ADHD and ADHD-associated behaviour.

1.3.2 Aim of this thesis

The aim of this study is to increase the knowledge about ADHD in VMBO students and promote a positive attitude towards people with ADHD through a workshop. The overall goal is to reduce public stigma of ADHD being the consequence of parental failure, substance abuse or the individual's own failure (19). Children with ADHD-associated behaviour are also more likely to be negatively judged by their peers (15). This is problematic, because peer-acceptance becomes more important in the teenage years (18). It is thus important to reduce stigma by increasing the VMBO students' knowledge about ADHD and by promoting a more positive attitude of the students in the VMBO-schools towards their peers with ADHD. By giving a workshop about ADHD, students with ADHD can also feel more heard and understood. Their quality of life and the feeling of social inclusion can increase (24).

1.4 Research question

This leads to the following research question: How does a workshop on ADHD change young peoples' understanding of and attitude towards people with ADHD at VMBO schools?

This main research question can be divided into the following sub questions:

- 1) Does giving a workshop about ADHD at VMBO schools increase the students' knowledge about ADHD?
- 2) Does giving a workshop about ADHD at VMBO schools generate a more positive attitude of the students towards peers with ADHD?
- 3) Do the teachers notice that VMBO students have a better understanding of and attitude towards people with ADHD in their classes after participating in the workshop?

Chapter 2: Methods

2.1 Research design

Both qualitative and quantitative data were collected to answer the main research question. We collected both data from three different groups: the focus group; the VMBO students; and the teachers (see *Chapter 2.2 Participants*). The qualitative and quantitative data from the VMBO students and the teachers were collected using question forms. The students received a question form before and after the workshop (see *Appendix 1.1 Pre-measurement question form VMBO students* and *Appendix 1.2 Post-measurement question form VMBO students*). Another source of data is gathered through observations made during the workshops. This qualitative data was used to provide a more nuanced insight to better understand the results. When observing, extra attention was paid to the reaction of the VMBO students, their attitude and the atmosphere of the class. With the help of the question forms for the VMBO students and the observations, sub questions 1 and 2 can be answered. The meeting with the focus group was used to support the answers in sub question 1 and 2.

To be able to answer sub question 3, the teachers received an evaluation form and a feedback form during the workshop and another evaluation form a month after the workshop is given (see *Appendix 1.3 Evaluation form teachers part 1* and *Appendix 1.4 Evaluation form teachers part 2*). The feedback form was used to provide feedback for the PhD student on their science communication (see *Appendix 1.5 Feedback form PhD students*). The feedback form and the second evaluation form were part of the ADHDplaza project, but did not form a part of this research. The analysis of the question forms will be explained in *Chapter 2.4 Methods of analysis*. A summary of our research design is seen in figure 1.

Figure 1: Research design of this study, including the research question, sub questions, data sources and the analysis.

2.2 Participants

2.2.1 Focus group

A focus group was set up to provide feedback on the website and on different components of the workshop. They also verified if these components resonated with the target group of VMBO students. The focus group consisted of 6 VMBO students (female=2; male=4) from 13-15 years old from Het Rhedens in Dieren. The female students were in VMBO-kl and the male students were in VMBO-t.

2.2.2 VMBO students

The workshops were given to 10 different classes divided over 7 different VMBO schools, consisting of 10-25 VMBO students. These students were in their first, second or third year of high school and were approximately 12-15 years old. The workshops were given to all VMBO levels: VMBO-bl (basiskader), VMBO-kl (kader) and VMBO-tl.

2.2.3 Teachers

The teachers present in each workshop received an evaluation form and a feedback form to be able to answer the third sub question. After a month, these teachers filled in a follow-up evaluation form.

2.3 Materials, techniques and instruments

The PowerPoint slides of the workshop can be found in *Appendix 2 Powerpoint workshop ADHDplaza*. This PowerPoint was made by team members of the ADHDplaza team.

2.3.1 Focus group

The focus group and two VMBO school teachers evaluated the workshop and provided feedback on the design, lay-out, structure and length of different components in the workshop, the content and the collaborative assignment. The focus group also contributed to the design and the colour palette of the PowerPoint and website of ADHDplaza. Three meetings were planned prior to the workshops and one meeting was planned after all the workshops have been given. The third meeting was planned after a trial workshop at Het Rhedens and was recorded using a voice recorder app on a mobile phone. These recordings were used to support our results answering sub question 1 and 2.

Prior to giving the workshops for the VMBO students, two VMBO school teachers provided a lesson on how to stand in front of a class, and to VMBO classes in particular, to the PhD students. During this lesson, the PhD students could ask questions and practice their performance.

2.3.2 Pre- and post-measurement question forms VMBO students

The pre- and post-measurement question forms given to the VMBO students consisted of 4 or 5 questions respectively, collecting qualitative data, and 5 statements, collecting quantitative data. In both question forms, we asked the VMBO students to rate their perceived knowledge about ADHD and their perceived empathy towards people with ADHD on a scale of 1 to 10. The students rated the statements using a 5-point Likert scale, ranking from totally disagree (scale 1) to totally agree (scale 5) (see *Appendix 1.1 Pre-measurement question form VMBO students* and *Appendix 1.2 Post-measurement question form VMBO students*). The statements in the question form were derived from different already existing scales or questionnaires used to measure stigma, assessing knowledge, behaviour and attitude (26). These already existing scales or measures assessing these aspects are the Mental Health Knowledge Schedule (MAKS), the Reported and Intended Behaviour Scale (RIBS) and the Community Attitude toward Mental Illness (CAMI), respectively (26). Table 1 shows the statements presented in the question forms and their derivation. The fourth statement is a combination between two statements from the CAMI scale. The fifth statement is not derived from a statement from an already existing scale or measure, but reflects a prejudice about ADHD (27). The questions and

statements in the question forms were evaluated on language and intelligibility by two teachers from VMBO schools and team members from the ADHDplaza project.

Table 1: Statements in the pre- and post-measurement forms for the students and their derivation. The different derivations are MAKS (Mental Health Knowledge Schedule), CAMI (Community Attitude toward Mental Illness) and RIBS (Reported and Intended Behaviour Scale).

Statement from existing scales/questionnaires	Statement in question form	What does it measure?
If a friend had a mental health problem, I know what advice to give them to get professional help	I know how to help a friend/ classmate with ADHD <i>Ik weet hoe ik een vriend/ klasgenoot met ADHD kan helpen</i>	Knowledge, MAKS (28, 29)
One of the main causes of mental illness is a lack of self-discipline and willpower	Problems with ADHD are your own fault <i>Problemen met ADHD zijn je eigen schuld</i>	Attitude, CAMI (30)
In the future, I would be willing to work with someone with a mental health problem	I would like to work together with someone with ADHD at school <i>Ik zou graag samenwerken met iemand met ADHD op school</i>	Behaviour, RIBS (31)
We have a responsibility to provide the best possible care for the mentally ill	We need to our best to help people with ADHD. <i>We moeten beter ons best doen om mensen met ADHD te helpen</i>	Attitude, CAMI (30)
We need to adopt a far more tolerant attitude toward people with mental illness in our society		
	ADHD is used as an excuse for bad behaviour <i>ADHD wordt gebruikt als smoes voor slecht gedrag</i>	Attitude

2.3.3 Evaluation form teachers

The evaluation form for the teachers was developed with the help of team members from the ADHDplaza project. The form consists of 2 questions and 6 statements, collecting qualitative and quantitative data. The teachers ranked the statements on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from totally disagree (scale 1) to totally agree (scale 5). The questions and statements were based on the aims the ADHDplaza project and the third sub question of this thesis and were not derived from already existing scales or measures.

2.4 Methods on analysis

All the collected data from the pre- and post-measurement question forms was put in Excel. Statistical analyses was done using IBM SPSS Statistics 27.

2.4.1 Observations during the workshop and focus group meeting

Observations were made during each workshop. When observing, extra attention was paid to the reaction of the VMBO students to the workshop, their participation during the workshop and the atmosphere of the class. The observations will help to improve the workshop and were used to provide a more nuanced insight in the results regarding the increase in knowledge and the change in attitude of the VMBO students.

After the trial workshop, the third focus group meeting was planned and recorded. Quotes were derived from this audio recording and used to support the results regarding the knowledge increase and the change in attitude of the VMBO students.

2.4.2 Pre- and post-measurement question forms VMBO students

The knowledge increase and the change in attitude were analysed in multiple ways. In the first and third question of both question forms, the VMBO students are asked to rank their perceived knowledge and empathy on ADHD on a scale of 1 to 10, respectively. The mean values of these questions were calculated using Excel. The means of these question were compared between the pre- and post-measurement question form using an independent T-test in SPSS. If $p < 0.05$, the perceived knowledge of the VMBO students about ADHD and the perceived empathy of these students towards people with ADHD has increased. When correcting for multiple testing, the p-value must be divided by 7, so $p < 0.007$. However, the means that are compared are not entirely independent from each other. Nonetheless, the data from the pre- and post-measurement question forms could not be paired because of ethical and logistical reasons, so a paired t-test is not possible. Therefore, we need to be careful in interpreting the p-values on these questions, because the data does not meet all the conditions of the statistical test.

In the second question of the question forms, the VMBO students were asked how they would describe a person with ADHD in 2-3 words. These words were categorized into general and summarizing terms ('busy' and 'very busy' were both categorized as 'busy'), which were then counted. The ten most described words in the pre-measurement question form were compared to the ten most described words in the post-measurement question form. When comparing these words, extra attention was paid to the association of the words with the content of the workshop. These words were marked. If the top ten most described themes in the post-measurement question form consisted of more words associated with the content of the workshop, the knowledge of the children had increased. Furthermore, I made a distinction between the positive and negative associated words of ADHD in the pre- and post-measurement question form. If the top ten most described themes in the post-measurement question form consisted of more positive words or characteristics associated with ADHD, the positive attitude of the VMBO students towards people with ADHD had increased.

The question forms also consisted of five statements, from which statement 1 measured knowledge and statement 2-5 measured attitude. The VMBO students rated these statements using a 5-point Likert scale. A 5-point Likert scale can be analysed through a parametric test or a nonparametric test. A nonparametric tests are less powerful, but they do not assume that the population is normally distributed (32). We chose to perform a nonparametric test to analyse the Likert scale responses, because we did not assumed that the gattered data followed a normal distribution. The Mann-Whitney U test was chosen as a nonparametric test to determine if there is a significant difference in knowledge and attitude between the pre- and post-measurement forms. The workshop had helped to increase the VMBO students' knowledge of and positive attitude towards people with ADHD if $p < 0.05$, and $p < 0.007$ when correcting for multiple testing. The interpretation of the p-values needed to be done carefully, because the data does not meet all the conditions of the statistical test.

Furthermore, the workshop was rated by the VMBO students on a scale of 1 to 5 in the post-measurement form. The mean of this question was calculated using SPSS.

2.4.3 Teacher's point of view

The evaluation form consisted of 2 questions and 6 statements. In the questions, the teachers were asked to describe how the students responded to the workshop, according to them, and if they were planning to discuss the subject ADHD more often in class and why. The given answers to the first question were categorized into common themes. The reappearing themes were counted. It was also counted how many teachers were planning on discussing the subject ADHD in class. In part 2 of the evaluation form, we asked the teachers whether they have discussed the subject ADHD in class. However, this will not be included in this analysis due to time constraints.

The statements were ranked on a 5-point Likert scale, ranking from totally disagree (scale 1) to totally agree (scale 5), evaluating the workshop and the aims of the ADHDplaza project. The median of each statement was calculated. These quantitative descriptive data was used to answer sub question 3, regarding the teachers' point of view on the increase in knowledge about ADHD and the change in attitude of the VMBO students towards people with ADHD.

2.5 Ethics

Prior to giving the workshop, a letter with information about the ADHDplaza project and an informed consent form was sent to the principle of the school. An informed consent form was also sent to the teacher of each class to ask for permission to use the data gathered during the workshop in this research. The teacher and the principle hereby gave consent to collect the following data in the workshop: the filled-in pre- and post-measurement question forms from the VMBO students; observations of the class and the response of the class to the workshop; and lastly the filled-in question forms and feedback form from the teacher. The question forms for the VMBO students are anonymous. The names of the students will not be used in the observations from the workshop. The VMBO students can thus not be traced and no personal information was collected.

An informed consent form was also sent to the VMBO students in the focus group, to ask for permission to use their feedback in this research and to record the focus group meetings. Both the students and their parents/caregivers had to sign this informed consent form. The names of the VMBO students will not be given when using quotes derived from the audio recordings.

2.6 Research data management

In this research both qualitative and quantitative data were collected through question forms, audio recordings and observations. The filled in question forms were scanned and stored in the secured Radboudumc drive on the genetics department. The physical question forms were stored in the secured archive room at the genetics department at the Radboudumc. This data will be stored for 10 years. Important quotes derived from the audio recordings from the focus group meeting were written down and the audio recordings were deleted at the end of this research.

Chapter 3: Results

3.1 Focus group

After the trial workshop, team members of the ADHDplaza project came together with the focus group to evaluate the trial workshop. The focus group opined the trial workshop educational. Someone in the focus group recognized a lot of characteristics mentioned during the workshop in his brother, who has ADHD. He said that the workshop did not help him to understand his brother better, because he already knew a lot about ADHD. Another person expressed that he knew not much about the disadvantages of having ADHD, but recognized a lot of the positive characteristics in peers from his soccer team. However, he did recognize that a lot of his team members often forgot something, but he did not know that this could be a characteristic of ADHD. Another person expressed that he also knew not much about ADHD and that this has changed after the workshop. He also expressed that he could empathize better with someone with ADHD after the workshop.

Another person also expressed that a lot of characteristics mentioned in the workshop were recognizable in people with ADHD. She thought that the workshop, and in particular the video shown during the workshop, had helped the class to have a better understanding of what ADHD entails. The girl in the video had ADHD and the VMBO students recognized that she had ADHD through the movements she made throughout the video, like playing with her hair the whole time.

The focus group expressed that a lesson series about ADHD would help the VMBO students to gain more knowledge about ADHD. In this way, the PhD students could go deeper into the negative and positive characteristics of ADHD and how ADHD is expressed in people.

3.2 VMBO students

There were 181 VMBO students who filled in the pre-measurement question form and 192 VMBO students who filled in the post-measurement question form. In the post-measurement question form, the VMBO students were asked to rate the workshop on a scale of 1 to 5. The mean score was 3.6 (SD=0.9).

3.2.1 Words associated with people with ADHD before and after the workshop

In the second question of both question forms, the VMBO students were asked how they would describe a person with ADHD in 2-3 words. The top 10 most named words in the pre- and post-measurement question forms are seen in table 1. The visualisation of the word count of all the words associated with ADHD according to the VMBO students in the pre- and post-measurement question form is seen in figure 2. The word 'busy/hyperactive' is named 140 times in the pre-measurement form and only 92 times in the post-measurement question form. There is also a difference in variation of words named and in the reoccurrence of words of both question forms. In the pre-measurement form, there are 3 words that reoccur a lot. These words are 'busy/hyperactive', 'concentration problems' and 'distracted'. In the post-measurement question form, there are 5 words that reoccur more often, namely 'busy/hyperactive', 'creative', 'concentration problems', 'distracted' and 'enthusiastic'.

The words named in the top 10 most named words associated with people with ADHD in the post-measurement question form are more positive than in the pre-measurement form. This is also visible in the top 3 of both question forms. The word "creative" is not named in the top 10 most named words in the pre-measurement question form and is in the second most-named word in the post-measurement question form. The words in the top 10 most named words associated with people with ADHD in the post-measurement question form are also more in line with the characteristics of ADHD explained during the workshop.

Table 1: top 10 most used words in pre- and post-measurement question forms for the VMBO students. Words are indicated with a '+' or '-' if they are positively or negatively associated with ADHD, respectively. Words that are in line with the characteristics explained during the workshop are indicated with a '*'.

TOP	PRE-MEASUREMENT	TRANSLATION	WEIGHT	POST-MEASUREMENT	TRANSLATION	WEIGHT
1	Druk (-)*	Busy/hyperactive	140	Druk (-)*	Busy/hyperactive	92
2	Concentratie problemen (-)*	Concentration problems	26	Creatief (+)*	Creative	24
3	Afgeleid (-)*	Distracted	21	Concentratie problemen (-)*	Concentration problems	22
4	Energiek (+)*	Energetic	8	Afgeleid (-)*	Distracted	16
5	Chaotisch (-)	Chaotic	6	Enthousiast (+)*	Enthusiastic	14
6	Onrustig (-)	Restless	6	Energiek (+)*	Energetic	9
7	Gezellig (+)	Social	5	Actief (+)*	Active	6
8	Vergeetachtig (-)*	Forgetful	5	Doorzettingsvermogen (+)*	Perseverance	5
9	Aandachtsproblemen (-)*	Attention problems	4	Impulsief (-)*	Impulsive	5
10	Actief (+)*	Active	4	Bewegelijk (-)*	Mobile	4

Figure 2: visualisation of the word count of the VMBO students' association with a person with ADHD from the measurement question forms. **A:** the pre-measurement question form. **B:** the post-measurement question form.

3.2.2 Perceived knowledge and empathy levels before and after the workshop

The perceived knowledge and empathy levels of the VMBO students before and after the workshop are visualized through a boxplot in figure 3. The increase in self-reported knowledge seems to be greater than the increase in self-reported empathy (mean knowledge pre-measurement=5.7 (SD=1.9), mean empathy pre-measurement=6.3 (SD=2.3), mean knowledge post-measurement=7.6 (SD=1.6), mean empathy post-measurement=7.1 (SD=2.1)). There is a significant increase in self-reported knowledge after the workshop, when not correcting for multiple testing ($p=0.016$) There is not a significant increase in self-reported empathy ($p=0.073$).

Figure 3: visualisation of the VMBO students’ self-reported knowledge and empathy levels before and after the workshop. **A:** visualisation of the self-reported knowledge levels. **B:** visualisation of the self-reported empathy levels.

3.2.3 Statements on knowledge and attitude

Figure 4 visualizes the responses of the VMBO students to the 5 statements in the question forms. The first statement measures knowledge (see figure 4A) and the other 4 statements measure attitude (see figure 4B-4E). There is a significant increase in knowledge seen after the workshop ($U=22192,500$, $p<0.001$). The difference between the pre- and post-measurement form is also visible in figure 4A. In the pre-measurement form, the graph shows a normal distribution where most students did not agree nor disagree with the statement “I know how to help a friend/classmate with ADHD”. In the post-measurement form, much more VMBO students agreed with the statement. However, the median at both measurement points was still 3.

Figure 4B shows the distribution of the statement “Problems with ADHD are your own fault”. This graph shows a right-skewed distribution for both the pre- and post-measurement question forms. Most VMBO students thus disagreed or totally disagreed with the statement in both question forms, which shows a positive attitude (median pre-measurement=1; median post-measurement=1). There was no significant difference in responses before and after the workshop ($U=15479,500$, $p=0.050$). Figure 4C shows the distribution of the statement “I would like to work together with someone with ADHD at school”. This graph shows a normal distribution for both the pre- and post-measurement question forms. Most students did not have an opinion about whether they wanted to work together with someone with ADHD (median pre-measurement=3; median post-measurement=3). There was no significant difference in responses before and after the workshop ($U=17923,000$, $p=0.480$). Figure 4D shows the distribution of the statement “We need to do our best to help people with ADHD”. At both measurement points, more VMBO students agreed or totally agreed with the statement than disagreed or totally disagreed, which shows a more positive attitude towards people with ADHD. However, the median at both measurement points is still 3. There was no significant difference in responses before and after the workshop ($U=16848,000$, $p=0.656$). Figure 4E shows the distribution of the statement “ADHD is used as an excuse for bad behaviour”. The VMBO students showed a more positive attitude towards ADHD at both measurement time points (median pre-measurement=2; median post-measurement=2). There was no significant difference in responses before and after the workshop ($U=17558,000$, $p=0.710$).

Figure 4: clustered bar plots of the rankings from the VMBO students on each of the 5 statements (A-E) in the measurement question forms, filtered by the time of measurement. The rank options ranging from totally disagree to totally agree are shown on the x-axis. The percentage of VMBO students voting for each of these options is shown on the y-axis.

3.3 Teachers' point of view

There were 12 teachers who completed the evaluation form, divided over 11 VMBO classes. This is because there were two teachers present during one workshop and they both completed the evaluation form. In the first question of the evaluation form, the teachers were asked to describe the reaction of the VMBO students to the workshop. The responses are visualised in figure 4. Three responses were named more than once: "recognition" (herkenning), "positive" (positief) and "the students participated well" (leerlingen deden goed mee).

Figure 5 : visualisation of the word count of question 1 in the teachers' evaluation form.

In the second question of the evaluation form, we asked the teachers if they would discuss the subject of ADHD more often in class. 6 teachers stated that they would discuss the subject of ADHD more often in class, 2 teachers were not sure and 4 teachers did not fill out this question. Some teachers said that they already had discussions in class about ADHD and were planning on discussing it more often. According to these teachers, it is important that everybody can be themselves and that requires understanding. Other teachers said that it would be wise to discuss the subject of ADHD more often. Two teachers were not sure whether to discuss the subject of ADHD more often in class. They felt like they were not qualified to teach a lesson about ADHD or they would only discuss the subject during a coaching hour with students with ADHD present in the classroom.

After the two open questions, the teachers had to rate 6 statements on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from totally disagree (scale 1) to totally agree (scale 5) (see Figure 6). The first 4 statements were in regard to the possible knowledge and empathy increase of the students and the teachers. All teachers, except one teacher, agreed or totally agreed with the statements "After the workshop about ADHD, the VMBO students have more knowledge about ADHD" (median=4) and "After the workshop about ADHD, the VMBO students have more empathy towards students with ADHD" (median=4).

4 teachers expressed to have gained more knowledge about ADHD after the workshop and 1 teacher expressed to have more empathy towards students with ADHD after the workshop. The other teachers voted neutral. The median of the statements regarding the knowledge and empathy increase of the teachers are both 3 (neutral).

Figure 6: bar plots of the first 4 statements (A-D) from the teachers’ evaluation form, evaluating the knowledge and empathy increase of the students and the teachers.

The last two statements in the evaluation form were in regard to the workshop itself (see figure 7). All teachers, except one, agreed or totally agreed with the statements “The workshop is in line with the experiences of the VMBO students” and “A workshop is a good way to reduce stigma about ADHD among VMBO students”. The medians of these two statements are 4 and 4.5, respectively.

Figure 7: bar plots of the last 2 statements (A-B) from the teachers’ evaluation form, evaluation the workshop.

Chapter 4: Discussion

In this pilot study, we examined the effect of a workshop about ADHD to VMBO students on their understanding of and attitude towards people with ADHD. This effect was measured by collecting data from three different groups: a focus group, VMBO students and their teachers. In addition to this, observations were made during the workshop to provide a more nuanced insight to better understand the results. The workshop significantly increased the VMBO students' understanding of ADHD, but was not enough to increase the positive attitude of the VMBO students towards people with ADHD. However, according to the teachers and the focus group, the attitude and empathy of the VMBO students did increase after the workshop.

The results of the pre-and post-measurement question forms for the VMBO students show a significant increase in knowledge of ADHD, but not a significant increase in empathy and positive attitude. This is also seen in the figures associated with the VMBO students' knowledge and attitude. However, according to the teachers, the workshop has helped to increase the VMBO students' understanding of and positive attitude towards people with ADHD. This opinion also matches the opinion of the focus group and my own observations. The VMBO students in most classes were curious about the characteristics of ADHD and asked a lot of questions during both parts of the workshop, which indicates that they learned something after the workshop. Discussions subsequently arose about the characteristics of ADHD or about how to help someone with ADHD. These discussions sometimes led to realisations of the VMBO students as to why people with ADHD behave in a certain way or why they can struggle with something other people without ADHD do not normally struggle with. The increase in understanding of ADHD could have led to more empathy towards people with ADHD in some VMBO students.

Furthermore, the top 10 most described words that the VMBO associated with people with ADHD in the post-measurement question form were more in line with the characteristics mentioned during the workshop and more positive. This also indicates an increase in understanding of and positive attitude towards people with ADHD in the VMBO students.

In the second half of the question forms, we asked the VMBO students to rate statements measuring knowledge and attitude on a 5-point Likert scale. There was a significant increase in knowledge after the workshop, but there was no difference seen between the statements in the pre- and post-measurement question form regarding attitude. However, positive attitudes were already apparent in some cases in the pre-measurement question form. For example, in statement 2 "problems with ADHD are your own fault", the positive attitude of the VMBO students could hardly increase after the workshop (median pre-measurement=1). The VMBO students also showed an already predominately positive attitude in the fourth and fifth statement of the measurement question forms ("We need to do our best to help people with ADHD" and "ADHD is used as an excuse for bad behaviour"). In conclusion, the attitude of the VMBO students towards people with ADHD was already predominately positive before the workshop, but there is room for improvement.

11 out of 12 teachers agreed that the workshop was in line with the experiences of the VMBO students and that a workshop about ADHD is a good way to reduce the stigma around it, which corresponds with existing literature (22). Multiple teachers we spoke to believed that the workshop also meant a lot to VMBO students with ADHD. Most of these students were actively participating in the workshop and were happy that the subject ADHD got talked about. They vocalized that they recognized a lot of positive and negative characteristics of ADHD as well as the difficulties that can come with having ADHD. These difficulties and problems were now acknowledged. It was explained that these problems were not just their own fault, but were because of their ADHD. Their peers could understand that now.

In the teachers' evaluation form, most teachers did not agree nor disagree with the statements regarding their own increase in knowledge about ADHD and empathy towards students with ADHD. This can be attributed to the fact that most teachers we spoke to had ADHD themselves or had an interest in the topic ADHD. They thus already knew a lot about ADHD. Most teachers also indicated that they will talk about ADHD more often in class after the workshop. They also said that it would be easier to talk about ADHD in the classroom after the workshop had been given.

This pilot study had some limitations. Firstly, the collected data was not entirely independent from each other. However, we were not able to obtain paired data to do a paired t-test due to practical and ethical reasons. The data did thus not meet all conditions of the statistical test, which led to a less reliable outcome. In the future, there need to be looked into possibilities to pair the data or make the data entirely independent from each other.

Secondly, the answers of the question forms for the VMBO students were purely subjective. The teachers involved in the ADHDplaza project advised us not to make the question forms too long and too difficult, because the VMBO students would lose their focus and not fill in the question forms. As a result, we had to be critical in which questions we wanted to ask the VMBO students. The statements were derived from already existing scales and measures assessing knowledge and attitude. However, we could not ask the VMBO to rate all the statements from these already existing scales, because not all statements were applicable for ADHD and it would make the question form too long. We could also not measure knowledge with questions measuring their actual knowledge, like is done in a test. This would also make the question form too long. We therefore chose to ask the students about their self-reported knowledge and empathy. However, some VMBO students greatly overestimated themselves according to their teachers. They think that they knew everything about ADHD after the workshop. Other VMBO students were more aware of the things they did not know yet about ADHD after the workshop and were more critical in answering these questions. In the future, there can be looked into other ways to measure knowledge and attitude to obtain more objective outcomes.

Thirdly, in this pilot study, we only measured the knowledge and attitude right before and after the workshop. The long-term effect of the workshop is yet to be investigated. The second evaluation form for the teachers still has to be sent out, filled in and analysed. The VMBO students may have learnt something after one workshop, but it is not known whether they will retain this gained knowledge. According to some teachers, VMBO students often need to hear information multiple times for them to remember it. The VMBO students' attitude may also not change after one workshop. This can take time. The long-term effect of knowledge and attitude should thus be investigated.

Some teachers suggested that a lesson series about ADHD would help to further increase the VMBO students' understanding of and positive attitude towards people with ADHD. One workshop might not be enough to reduce the stigma around ADHD in the long term. A lesson series about ADHD would help to actively engage the VMBO students in the subject. A lesson series would also help to repeat the main message we want to convey multiple times, which helps to increase the chances of the VMBO students remembering the main message. It would thereby increase their long term understanding of and attitude towards people with ADHD. In the future, there can be looked into creating a lesson series about ADHD and investigating the effect of these lesson series.

In this study, we mainly focused on increasing the understanding of and attitude towards people with ADHD in VMBO students, because we assumed that the percentage of students with ADHD was the highest in VMBO-schools due to their association with lower IQ and more poorly rated academic abilities (2, 16). There are however also misconceptions about ADHD, students with ADHD and a negative attitude from their peers towards people with ADHD in every school level. There is thus also

a need to reduce stigma here. In the future, there can be looked into giving workshops about ADHD and investigating the effect of these workshops to students in other school levels. Each school level will need another lay-out and structure of the workshop since students from each school level learn differently and at a different pace.

There can also be looked into educating teachers on the topic ADHD. Student from the pilot study done at the start of the ADHDplaza project had to explain to their teacher what ADHD entails (25). This is problematic since ADHD is a common neurodevelopmental disorder with a high prevalence among children and adolescents. Each teacher is thus likely to have a student with ADHD in their classroom. Stigma around ADHD among teachers needs to be reduced for the students with ADHD to feel safe and understood in the classroom. The effect of educating teachers on the subject ADHD on the understanding of and attitude towards people with ADHD can be investigated. If this has a positive effect, the teachers could use the designed workshop to educate their students on the subject of ADHD. This would prevent or solve possible organizational issues around hiring people to give the workshops to students. The teachers see the students more often than someone else giving the workshop and can therefore more easily increase the students' understanding of ADHD and also promote a more positive attitude towards people with ADHD, which will reduce stigma around it.

Chapter 5: Conclusions and translational aspects

One workshop about ADHD leads to a significant increase in the VMBO students' understanding of ADHD, but was not enough to significantly increase their positive attitude towards ADHD. However, the VMBO students associated more positive characteristics with people with ADHD after the workshop, which indicates a slightly more positive attitude towards ADHD after the workshop. In addition to that, the teachers and the focus group believed that the knowledge and empathy of the VMBO students had increased after one workshop. A lesson series about ADHD might help to increase the VMBO students' understanding of and positive attitude towards people with ADHD further. In the future, there can also be looked into expanding the workshop to other school levels and educating teachers on the subject of ADHD.

If the workshop can be expanded and students and teachers obtain more accurate knowledge about ADHD, stigma around ADHD can decrease and the societal impact will be considerable. Students with ADHD from the pilot study at the start of the ADHDplaza project indicated that it would help if more attention was paid to ADHD at school. Other people with ADHD I spoke with expressed that it would have helped them a lot if more attention was paid to ADHD at school and the stigma around ADHD was reduced. According to the teachers we spoke to after the workshops, the workshop had also meant a lot to the VMBO students with ADHD. They felt heard and felt like their problems and difficulties because of their ADHD were acknowledged. It also meant a lot to them to hear that these problems were not per se their fault, but were because of their ADHD. After the workshop, their peers could understand that. A workshop about ADHD is thus a good way to reduce stigma around ADHD.

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ADHDplaza – les op school

Vragen vooraf

Hallo! Wij onderzoeken wat jullie vinden van (de les over) ADHD. Je hoeft je naam niet op te schrijven, dus niemand weet wat jij hebt ingevuld. Het is heel belangrijk dat je de vragen eerlijk invult. Succes!

1. Hoeveel weet je over ADHD op een schaal van 1 tot 10? Kleur de driehoek in tot waar van toepassing is.

2. Hoe zou je iemand met ADHD beschrijven in 2-3 woorden?

3. In hoeverre kan jij je inleven in iemand met ADHD op een schaal van 1 tot 10? Kleur de driehoek in tot waar van toepassing is. Je in iemand kunnen inleven betekent bijvoorbeeld dat je begrijpt wat iemand voelt of meemaakt.

4. Wat wil jij weten over ADHD?

Nu komen een paar stellingen. Kleur het rondje in die past bij wat jij vindt. Hiermee geef je aan of je het 'helemaal niet eens', 'niet mee eens', 'neutraal', 'mee eens' of 'helemaal eens' bent met de stelling.

Let op: vul alleen in wat jij zelf vindt. Er is geen goed of fout antwoord.

Stelling	Helemaal niet mee eens	Niet mee eens	Neutraal	Mee eens	Helemaal mee eens
Ik weet hoe ik een vriend/ klasgenoot met ADHD kan helpen	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Problemen met ADHD zijn je eigen schuld	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Ik zou graag samenwerken met iemand met ADHD op school	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
We moeten beter ons best doen om mensen met ADHD te helpen	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
ADHD wordt gebruikt als smoes voor slecht gedrag	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

ADHDplaza – les op school

Vragen achteraf

Hallo! Wij onderzoeken wat jullie vinden van (de les over) ADHD. Je hoeft je naam niet op te schrijven, dus niemand weet wat jij hebt ingevuld. We willen weten wat je nú denkt, dus het maakt niet uit wat je de vorige keer hebt ingevuld. Het is heel belangrijk dat je de vragen eerlijk invult. Succes!

1. Hoeveel weet je nu over ADHD op een schaal van 1 tot 10? Kleur de driehoek in tot waar van toepassing is.

2. Hoe zou je nu iemand met ADHD beschrijven in 2-3 woorden?

3. In hoeverre kan jij je inleven in iemand met ADHD op een schaal van 1 tot 10? Kleur de driehoek in tot waar van toepassing is. Je in iemand kunnen inleven betekent bijvoorbeeld dat je begrijpt wat iemand voelt of meemaakt.

4. Wat zouden onderzoekers volgens jou nog moeten onderzoeken over ADHD?

5. Wat vond je van deze les? Kleur de smiley in die voor jou van toepassing is.

Nu komen een paar stellingen. Kleur het rondje in die past bij wat jij vindt. Hiermee geef je aan of je het ‘helemaal niet eens’, ‘niet mee eens’, ‘neutraal’, ‘mee eens’ of ‘helemaal eens’ bent met de stelling.

Let op: vul alleen in wat jij zelf vindt. Er is geen goed of fout antwoord.

Stelling	Helemaal niet mee eens	Niet mee eens	Neutraal	Mee eens	Helemaal mee eens
Ik weet hoe ik een vriend/ klasgenoot met ADHD kan helpen	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Problemen met ADHD zijn je eigen schuld	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Ik zou graag samenwerken met iemand met ADHD op school	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
We moeten beter ons best doen om mensen met ADHD te helpen	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
ADHD wordt gebruikt als smoes voor slecht gedrag	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

ADHDplaza – Les op school

Evaluatieformulier docenten deel 1

Beste docent, vandaag geven wij aan uw leerlingen een les over ADHD. Het doel van deze les is om de kennis over ADHD bij de leerlingen te vergroten en meer begrip bij de leerlingen over ADHD te genereren. Daarnaast hebben wij informatie verzameld over hoe leerlingen denken over ADHD en wat zij graag willen weten over ADHD. Om te toetsen of dit eerste doel behaald is, hebben wij een aantal vragen voor u. Over een maand sturen wij u nog een korte vragenlijst om beide doelen te evalueren. Wij zouden het op prijs stellen als u deze vragenlijst binnen een week na de les terugstuurt. Alvast bedankt!

Met vriendelijke groet,

Martine Hoogman, Jeanette Mostert, Lessa Schippers en Maike Schoonbergen

1. Hoe reageerden de leerlingen volgens u op de les?

2. Bent u van plan om het onderwerp van ADHD vaker te bespreken in de klas na de les, en waarom wel of niet?

Hieronder staan een paar stellingen. Kruis het vakje aan dat past bij uw mening.

Stellingen	Helemaal niet mee eens	Niet mee eens	Neutraal	Mee eens	Helemaal mee eens
Na de les over ADHD, weten de leerlingen meer over ADHD					
Na de les over ADHD, weet ik zelf meer over ADHD					
Na de les over ADHD, hebben de leerlingen meer begrip voor leerlingen met ADHD					
Na de les over ADHD, heb ik zelf meer begrip voor leerlingen met ADHD					
De les over ADHD sluit aan bij de belevingswereld van de leerlingen					
Een les over ADHD is een goede manier om stigma over ADHD onder leerlingen te verminderen					

Heeft u verder nog opmerkingen over de les?

ADHDplaza – Les op school

Evaluatieformulier docenten deel 2

Beste docent, onlangs hebben wij aan uw leerlingen een les gegeven over ADHD. Het doel van deze les is om de kennis over ADHD bij de leerlingen te vergroten en meer begrip bij de leerlingen over ADHD te genereren. Daarnaast hebben wij informatie verzameld over hoe leerlingen denken over ADHD en wat zij graag willen weten over ADHD. Om te toetsen of deze doelen behaald zijn, hebben wij een aantal vragen voor u. Wij zouden het op prijs stellen als u deze vragenlijst binnen een week terugstuurt. Alvast bedankt!

Met vriendelijke groet,

Martine Hoogman, Jeanette Mostert, Lessa Schippers en Maike Schoonbergen

1. Heeft u het met de leerlingen nog een keer gehad over de les en/of over ADHD?

JA / NEE

2. Zo ja, wat hebben jullie besproken? Zo nee, waarom niet?

3. Heeft de les volgens u bijgedragen aan een verandering in kennis over ADHD bij de leerlingen?

JA / NEE

4. Wat is u hierin opgevallen?

5. Heeft de les volgens u bijgedragen aan een verandering in houding ten opzichte van ADHD bij de leerlingen?

JA / NEE

6. Wat is u hierin opgevallen?

7. Heeft u nog ideeën hoe wij als onderzoekers kunnen bijdragen aan kennis over ADHD op scholen?

ADHDplaza – Les op school

Feedbackformulier

Beste docent, wij geven vandaag een les over ADHD in uw klas. Het doel van deze les is om de kennis over ADHD bij de leerlingen te vergroten en meer begrip bij de leerlingen over ADHD te genereren. Een les geven die aansluit bij de doelgroep en het hebben van goede presentatievaardigheden zijn hierbij van groot belang. Om de les en de presentatievaardigheden van de onderzoekers te evalueren, hebben wij een aantal onderdelen van de les benoemd. Wij zouden het op prijs stellen als u deze onderdelen wil beoordelen en dit formulier aan het einde van de les terug geeft. Alvast bedankt!

Met vriendelijke groet,

Martine Hoogman, Jeanette Mostert, Lessa Schippers en Maike Schoonbergen

Onderdelen van de les	Matig	Redelijk	Neutraal	Goed	Heel goed
Structuur van de les					
Inhoud van de les					
Presentatievaardigheden van de onderzoeker(s)					
Enthousiasme van de onderzoekers					
Duidelijkheid van de boodschap van de les					

Hieronder staan nog een keer de onderdelen van de les. Als u nog tips of tops heeft over verschillende onderdelen, kunt u dat hieronder opschrijven.

Onderdelen van de les	Tips en tops
Structuur van de les	
Inhoud van de les	
Presentatievaardigheden van de onderzoekers	
Enthousiasme van de onderzoekers	
Duidelijkheid van de boodschap van de les	
Overig	

Appendix 2: PowerPoint workshop ADHDplaza

The PowerPoint slides of the workshop can be found in the document attached to this thesis. These slides were used in the trial workshop at Het Rhedens in Dieren.